

CONSTITUTION OF THE SEEDS OF *BLEPHARIS EDULIS*, PERS. PART II. THE COMPOSITION OF THE OIL

BY G. P. PENDSE AND JAGRAJ BEHARI LAL.

A bitter glucoside *Blepharin* ($C_{16}H_{20}O_{11}$, m.p. 222°) and *dl*-allantoin were isolated from the seeds of *Blepharis edulis*, Pers (Lal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 109). The present paper deals with the composition of the oil obtained from the seeds by exhaustive extraction with benzene. It has been found that the oil contains oleic and linolic acids in the unsaturated portion and palmitic, stearic and arachidic acid in the saturated portion of the fatty acids. The unsaponifiable matter is identified to be a sterol. The oil on standing for over three days deposited a sterol identified to be arni-diol (*cf.* Klobb, *Compt. rend.*, 1904, 138, 763; 1905 140, 1700).

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

9 Kg. of the powdered seeds on exhaustive extraction with benzene yielded 342 g. (3.8%) of a thick reddish brown oil possessing the characteristic odour of the drug. The crude oil was purified in the usual way. It deposited a small amount of a light brown solid on standing for 2-3 days. It is free from nitrogen or sulphur and has been found to belong to the class of semi-drying oils. The chemical and physical constants of the oil are given in Table I. 150 G. of the oil were saponified in the usual way. The constants of the fatty acids are given in Table II.

TABLE I.

Optical rotation	[α] _D ²⁰ - 8.4	Sapon. value	186.5
Sp. gr.	0.9332 at 28°	Acetyl value	11.54
Viscosity	8.35 (compared to Rape oil).	Hehner's value	91.65
Ref. index	1.4846 at 30°	Iodine value	90.8
Solidifying point	-3°	Unsaponifiable matter	2.5-3%
Acid value	11.85		

TABLE II.

Consistency	Semi-solid.	Neutralisation value	180.8
Sp. gr.	0.9054 at 30°	Mean M. W.	309.5
Ref. index	1.4796	Iodine value	92.5

The mixture of the fatty acids was then separated into the saturated and unsaturated acids by Twitchell's method (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806). During the separation of the acids a small amount of a resinous mass, insoluble in ether, was separated. Table III gives the percentage, mean M. W. and iodine values of the saturated and unsaturated acids.

TABLE III.

Acids.	% of the mixed acids.	% in the oil.	Iodine value.	Mean M. W.
Saturated	12.38	11.34	2.6	276
Unsaturated	87.62	80.3	104.7	270.2

Examination of the Unsaturated Acids.

The unsaturated acids were systematically examined by oxidation with potassium permanganate. The absence of hexahydroxystearic acid proved the absence of linolenic acid. Two acids, dihydroxystearic acid and tetrahydroxystearic acid, were isolated by extraction with ether and hot water. These two acids showed the presence of oleic and linolic acids in the mixed liquid acids.

The quantitative examination of the unsaturated acids was done by the method of Jamieson and Baughman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 1197) by preparing their bromo-addition products. The hexabromo derivative of linolenic acid is insoluble in cold ether; since no precipitate insoluble in ether was found, the absence of linolenic acid was confirmed. The ether-soluble portion was dissolved in petroleum ether and cooled when crystals of linolic tetrabromide (m. p. 113-14°) separated showing the presence of linolic acid. The residue was evaporated to dryness and the bromine content estimated. Table IV gives the results of the analysis of the bromo-addition products.

TABLE IV.

Wt. of the unsaturated acids	4.4632 g.
Linolic acid tetrabromide	1.2364
Residue (di- and tetrabromides)	6.0138 (Br, 36.68%)
Dibromo-oleic acid in the residue	5.8388 (97.1%)
Tetrabromolinolic acid in the residue	0.1749 (2.9%)
Total tetrabromolinolic acid	1.4113
Linolic acid equivalent to the tetrabromide	0.7305 (16.37%)
Oleic acid equivalent to the dibromide	3.7252 (83.45%)

The iodine value of the mixture of the unsaturated acids was found to be 104.7. Table V contains the percentage of the linolic and oleic acids calculated by the bromine addition method and from the iodine values.

TABLE V.

	Bromine addition method.			Calc. from the iodine values.		
	In the unsaturated acids.	In the total fatty acids.	In the original oil.	In the unsaturated acids.	In the total fatty acids.	In the original oil.
Oleic acid	83.45%	72.75%	66.56%	83.93%	73.16%	67.04%
Linolic acid	16.37	14.27	13.08	16.07	14.00	12.83

Examination of the Saturated Acids.

The saturated acids separated from the mixed acids were freed from traces of liquid acids by pressing over a porous plate. The acids, thus obtained, are yellowish white in colour, m. p. 54-55°.

The mixture of the acids was converted into the methyl esters and 10 g. of the esters were distilled under reduced pressure. The iodine values and the saponification values of the different fractions were determined and the mean M. W. calculated. The mean molecular weight of methyl palmitate is 270.3 and that of methyl stearate 298.4. The mean molecular weights of the first three fractions lie between these two values and therefore indicate a mixture of the two. The mean molecular weight of the last fraction is greater than

298 and hence contains the ester of an acid of higher molecular weight. The free acid obtained from the last fraction melted at about 71-73°, pointing it to be a mixture of arachidic acid and stearic acid. The percentages of the acids were determined in the different fractions by means of their iodine values and mean molecular weights (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920 **42**, 152). Tables VI and VII contain the results of the analysis.

TABLE VI.

Frac-tions.	B. p.	Wt. of frac-tions.	M. p. of free acids.
1	180-200°/1.5 mm.	2.28 g.	63-64°
2	200-20°/1 mm.	3.64	64°
3	220-35°/1 mm.	0.84	66-68°
4	Residue above 240°	3.24	71-73°

Examination of the Unsaponifiable Matter.

The unsaponifiable matter (3%) was dissolved in ether and washed with water repeatedly to remove the adhering soap. The dried ethereal solution was distilled when a yellowish white sticky matter was obtained. On repeated crystallisations from alcohol white silky flakes were obtained, m. p. 115-117°, (α)_D²⁰ (in chloro form), -35°. From the colour reactions the unsaponifiable matter was identified to be a phytosterol. [Found: C, 78.0; H, 10.33. C₂₇H₄₇O, 2 H₂O (?) requires C, 77.92; H, 10.6 per cent].

TABLE VII.

Frac-tion.	Iodine values.	Sapon. value.	Mean M. W.	Esters of unsaturated acids.	M. W. of saturated acids.	Palmitic acid.	Stearic acid.	Arachidic acid.	Unsaturated acid.
1	2.4	201.66	275.5	2.42% (0.055 g.)	275.25	1.735 g. (76.18%)	0.36 g. (16.39%)		0.052 g. (2.3%)
2	1.6	198.46	262.8	1.61% (0.059 g.)	262.8	2.20 (60.31%)	1.21 (33.74%)		0.057 (1.53%)
3	1.2	192.6	291.35	1.22% (0.01 g.)	291.4	0.20 (23.2%)	0.59 (74.18%)		0.0095 (1.16%)
4	0.8	187.2	299.7	0.81% (0.03 g.)	299.8		3.03 (93.62%)	0.009 (0.9%)	0.0285 (0.8%)

Examination of the Solid separated from the Oil.

The light brown solid which was deposited from the oil was filtered and pressed on a porous plate. It was then washed with benzene in the cold to remove the adhering oil. A light brown coloured amorphous solid (1 g.) was thus obtained. The amorphous powder was extracted repeatedly with boiling alcohol which on cooling deposited a crystalline solid, m. p. 249-50°. A little of the amorphous powder was insoluble in alcohol and did not yield any crystalline product.

The crystalline solid answered to Salkowski's test, hydrochloric acid test, and Burchard-Liebermann's tests and was proved to be a phytosterol. The sterol appears to be identical with arnidiol described by Klabb (*loc. cit.*). [Found : C, 79.86; H, 11.26. $C_{28}H_{44}(OH)_2$ requires C, 81.15; H, 11.11 per cent].

Sterol from *Blepharis edulis* oil.

M. p., 249-50°

$[\alpha]_D^{25}$, -61.5

(in chloroform solution)

Diacetyl derivative,
m. p. 96-98°

Arnidiol.

M. p., 249-50°

$[\alpha]_D^{25}$, -62.8

Diacetyl derivative, m. p. 100°

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
VICTORIA COLLEGE,
GWAJALIOR STATE.

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